

field; and diagonal, diagonally across the field, with 2 replications.

Sampling was done weekly from seedling stage until 60 d after transplanting in 20- × 50-m plots planted to IR64. No insecticide was applied.

Samples were obtained by sweeping while walking at a normal pace along the prescribed pattern. Sampling was done early in the morning. Three 10-sweep samples were taken for each plot—the first from the edge of the plot toward the middle, the second in the middle, and the third from the middle toward the end of the plot.

Density estimates for GLH population were similar, regardless of the sampling pattern (see figure). □

GLH (no./10 sweeps)

Density estimates of GLH population monitored by sweep net sampling along a fixed path in each of the 3 sweep net sampling patterns evaluated in field plots planted to IR64. Carmen, Bohol, Philippines, Aug-Nov 1987.

Yield losses due to rice gall midge (GM)

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When heavy GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason) infestation occurred in seed plots at experimental stations in 1987-88 wet season, we took the opportunity to study yield losses.

Yield losses caused by GM. Batalagoda, Sri Lanka, 1987-88 wet season.

Cultivar	Regression equation (yield in g/hill)	Regression ^a (r value)	% yield loss/% incidence
Bg 3-5	$Y = 28.08 - 0.265 X$	0.49**	0.92
Bg 38	$Y = 20.08 - 0.110 X$	0.33*	0.52
Bg 400-1	$Y = 18.61 - 0.20 X$	0.65**	1.07
Bg 379-2	$Y = 26.76 - 0.230 X$	0.59**	0.85
Bg 34-6	$Y = 10.821 - 0.065 X$	0.43 ^{ns}	0.60
Bg 350	$Y = 7.18 - 0.056 X$	0.35 ^{ns}	0.78
Bg 94-1	$Y = 9.67 - 0.028 X$	0.24 ^{ns}	0.29
Bg 34-8	$Y = 15.87 - 0.14 X$	0.36*	0.88
Bg 276-5	$Y = 12.56 - 0.11 X$	0.42*	0.89

^a Significant at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ns = not significant.

Number of tillers and number of silvershoots were recorded at flowering in 100 randomly tagged hills of 9 cultivars.

The regression between grain

yield/hill on GM incidence (GMI) was calculated. Grain yields were negatively correlated with GM in all cultivars (see table). □

Effect of flooding on Malayan black bug (MBB) egg hatching and parasitoid emergence

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The MBB *Scotinophara coarctata* lays its eggs at the base of rice plants. We studied the effects of flooding on unparasitized eggs and eggs parasitized by *Telenomus triptux*

To determine the effects of flooding on egg hatching, egg masses were put in test tubes filled with water for 0, 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 h, in 10 replications. To determine the effect of submergence on parasitoid emergence, freshly laid eggs of MBB were placed in a parasite colony

for 24 h. After parasitoid oviposition, the eggs were submerged for 0, 2, 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 h.

When egg masses were not submerged, 96% hatched; none hatched after submergence for 24 h (see figure). When submerged 6, 12, and 18 h, only 33, 29, and 3% hatched, respectively. Unparasitized eggs submerged for 24 h did not hatch. However, more than 50% of the parasitoids emerged after 24 h submergence (see figure). □

Effect of pesticides on germination and growth of three fungi of rice insects

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Populations of rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) in the field and in insect-rearing cages are commonly infected with specific fungi (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes). Conidia of the fungi germinate on the insect cuticle, and penetration follows. The mycelium multiplies in the hemocoel by yeast-like budding.

Effect of flooding on MBB egg hatchability and parasitoid emergence. IRRI, 1988.

Fungal species, strains, and their ARSEF numbers.^a

Fungus species	Strain	ARSEF
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	BbE	714
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Ma12	1432
<i>Hirsutella citriformis</i>	Hc490	490

^aUSDA-ARS Collection of Entomopathogenic Fungal Cultures, USDA-ARS Plant Protection Unit, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research at Cornell University, Tower Road, Ithaca, NY 14853-0331, USA; the isolates are also available from the Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute.

Conidia produced on the outside of the cadaver can infect healthy BPH. Insect fungus epizootics can completely control BPH populations.

Several chemical pesticides that suppress germination and growth of the insect fungi can prevent the occurrence of epizootics. We designed an experiment to illustrate these effects and to provide a simple test for studying the interaction between fungi and chemicals.

Three BPH pathogens—*Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill., *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch.) Sorokin, and *Hirsutella citriformis* Speare—were treated (see table) with technical formulations of the fungicides benomyl and edifenphos and the insecticide carbaryl.

Germination rates were determined by incubating 10⁶ conidia/ml of a 1% dextrose/0.5% yeast extract broth on a shaker machine. Pesticides were applied at 0.1, 1, 10, 100, and 1,000 ppm in 5 replications. After 24 h, at least 250 conidia of each replication were examined under the microscope for the presence of germination tubes. Germination rates were computed as

$$\text{germination (\%)} = 100\% \times \frac{\text{no. germinated conidia}}{\text{no. germinated conidia} + \text{no. not germinated conidia}}$$

Mycelium growth rates were determined in a 3% dextrose/1.5% yeast extract broth in shaker flasks. The flasks were inoculated with 1 ml conidia suspension (5 × 10⁶ conidia/ml). Mycelium dry weight was determined after 3 d of growth.

All concentrations of the pesticides tested inhibited conidia germination (see figure). *H. citriformis* was significantly

Effects of the pesticides benomyl, carbaryl, and edifenphos on the germination and mycelium growth of the insect fungi *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, and *H. citriformis*.

more susceptible to benomyl at 10 and 100 ppm concentrations.

Such simple laboratory assays can be used to evaluate selective effects of

pesticides on insect fungi. Use of inhibiting compounds (such as benomyl) should be avoided during insect fungus epizootics. □

A simplified method for sampling leaffolders (LFs) and planthoppers

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We developed a sequential sampling plan and designed a simple pegboard for recording LF, planthopper (brown planthopper [BPH] and whitebacked planthopper [WBPH]), and predator field populations. The goal was a simplified procedure that farmers can use in making IPM decisions.

Sampling models were based on distribution patterns and thresholds generated on the IRRI farm; in Mabitac and Liliw towns, Laguna; and in several fields in Batangas, Philippines.

LF distribution fitted the negative binomial distribution with a clumping coefficient (K) of 1.1. Thresholds were 1-2 larvae/hill, assuming a 20% chance of making an incorrect pest control decision.

Sequential sampling for BPH and WBPH was based on a binomial distribution model. It was developed from a regression curve drawn by correlating percentage of hills infested